

Machines Translating the Qur'an

A Comparative Analysis of AI and Human Generated Translations

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Abstract

This article presents what to the best of the author's knowledge is the first large-scale comparative study of Qur'an translations generated by Large Language Models (LLMs). Fifteen different LLMs were prompted to translate the Qur'an from Arabic to English, and the resulting translations were compared with human-produced translations. Using both lexical and semantic similarity measures, the study reveals that LLM translations exhibit significant influence from existing human translations, particularly the translation known as *Sahih International*, while also demonstrating creative capacities when confronted with ambiguities. Additionally, the article introduces a bottom-up, LLM-augmented methodology for comparative translation analysis using sentence embeddings, enabling efficient verse-by-verse comparison across translations. This study contributes to the emerging field examining non-human representations of Islam and raises questions about the future role of AI in mediating access to sacred texts.

Keywords: Large Language Models (LLMs); Qur'an translation; Sahih International; comparative translation analysis; sentence embeddings; non-human Islam; artificial intelligence; Islamic studies

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In October 2023, Talal Itani, an electronics engineer and Qur'an translator, published a new online translation of the Qur'an, *sureQuran*, to complement his previous *ClearQuran*. (Itani 2023b) On the website devoted to dissemination (<https://www.surequran.com>), Itani explicitly acknowledges that he has made use of 'Artificial Intelligence' in the translation process. What Itani here most likely refers to is the technology of generative AI that rests on so-called Large Language Models (henceforth LLMs).

There are a plethora of such models available at the time of writing. In his short article on the process, published online, Itani does not specify the LLM he used, but he does assure the reader that he, Itani, has not left the work to the 'AI' alone, but that he has been the so-called human-in-the-loop, the final arbiter, throughout the process. (Itani 2023a)

The question arises why anyone would bother to go to Itani's website to get an AI translation of the Qur'an, not only into English, but into any language. Chatbots such as ChatGPT, Claude, Gemini, Le Chat, or DeepSeek (just to mention a few large ones at the time of writing) are becoming increasingly available, often for free, to anyone with access to the Internet. They all have the capacity to provide translations of the Qur'an.

Not everyone embraces this new technology as enthusiastically as Itani. The ambitious research project addressing translations of the Qur'an into languages other than the original Arabic, *The Global Qur'an*, led by Islamic studied scholar Johanna Pink, has a blog where they publish short texts on diverse Qur'an translations that they discover and analyse. Pink herself, in one post from September 24, 2024, has spotted a translation on sale on Amazon that is obviously a machine translation. She identifies it as a translation of a poorly OCR read Spanish translation, which is then something different than *sureQuran*, not necessarily using an LLM. However, towards the end of the blog post, Pink does comment upon the rise of generative artificial intelligence and the issue of Qur'an translations. She writes:

The problem [of identifying the original work behind a translation] will be exacerbated once we have translations that are produced by large language models, using the works of countless human translators, whether they are still under copyright protection or not, without crediting anyone. A skilled publisher could easily use AI to come up with a decent translation, a plausible translator's persona, title page, and blurbs, resulting in a product that will fool anyone. Maybe such translations are already on the market and we just do not know it. (Pink 2024)

They are. Itani's is one. As a preparation for the current article, I have myself produced an additional 15. The purpose is not commercial, however, but research.

The current article has two objectives. The first is to describe the very process of producing LLM translations, without any (direct) involvement of a human translator. The second is to compare the results of the process, both between LLMs and between LLMs and human translations, with the specific goal to evaluate the extent to which, and in what manner, these LLMs are using 'the works of countless human translators'.

Why is this relevant?

In the quotation above, Pink voices a rather negative view on the prospect of LLM translations of the Qur'an, presenting them as parasitic on human translations. Regardless of how we view the development, it is a fact that generative artificial intelligence is rapidly changing the world, including the world of religion and of Islam.

People are already relying heavily on information provided by chatbots and other systems of generative AI, and this reliance is not likely to diminish. In the context of translations of the Qur'an, it is conceivable that published Qur'ans will not be the main source used for assessing content of the sacred scripture. Such information will be provided on the fly by artificial systems, integrated into our everyday electronic devices. The demand for professional translators and established publishing firms will be less. This development makes it even more important to try to assess what kind of translations systems of generative AI produce. Perhaps even more so when it comes to translations of the Qur'an than many other texts.

As is well known, translations of the Qur'an have been ridden with controversy. According to the dominant Islamic tradition, the Qur'an was revealed to the Prophet Muhammad in a 'clear Arabic'. This was the language that God chose for communicating with mankind. Based on this, there is an oft-repeated notion that the Qur'an cannot be translated, at least not in a manner that preserves its 'true' meaning. All translations are *human* interpretations, and as such defective. There is here also a theological connection to the notion of *i'jāz*, or the inimitability of the Qur'an. Albeit this concept refers to a wider notion of the exceptional status of the Qur'an, in style and content, it also covers linguistic aspects.

Still, the Qur'an has been translated, even early on in history to a multitude of languages. The inventory that is part of the *Global Qur'an project* testifies to this. Admittedly, in the case of Muslim translators, translations have often been framed as a form of *tafsīr*, i.e. as 'interpretation' or 'commentary', in a gesture of deference to the notion of *i'jāz*. Non-Muslim translators have generally not displayed similar deference. At times, translations have stirred controversy, in modern times not so much because of a reluctance to the act of translating as such, but more connected to real or assumed biases of the translators. This includes not only the works of non-Muslim translators, be they orientalists or Christian missionaries, but also the works of members of the Ahmadiyya movement, or such idiosyncratic translations as that of Rashad Khalifa.

There are entire works devoted to evaluating translations,¹ and specific studies targeted at discovering 'sectarian' or ideological influences in translations, (Robinson 1997) or studies exploring for example the influence on the translator's gender on translations. (Hassen 2012)

What all such attempts at evaluation have in common is that they assume a human 'mind' at work in the translation process. This mind houses an 'inner world' of beliefs, motives, emotions, personal characteristics, knowledge, limitations etc that stands in an imagined causal relationship to the outcome, i.e. the translation. This is an important difference to the case under study here. In LLM translations, no such 'inner world' exists. The translation is merely a consequence of training on enormous amounts of data and probability distributions as a result of highly complex calculations.

What follows is, to my knowledge, the first large scale comparative study of AI translations of the Qur'an.² Since it is the first attempt, the scope is broad. But it also extends beyond the immediate context of translations. The present article is also a contribution to an emerging research field within Islamic studies, the study of non-Muslim Islams. Since its inception, Islamic studies largely have concerned itself with attempts at understanding the origin and development of Islam as a discursive tradition. (Asad 2009) A large portion of the data has been public statements on what 'Islam is' produced by individuals and groups who self-identify as Muslims. In a recent article in *Method and Theory in the Study of*

¹ For an ambitious example comparing translations into English, see Kidwai (2011).

² For other, more limited, recent studies, mainly from a theologically oriented perspective, see Al Ghamdi and Khan (2022); Dahia and Belbacha (2024); Khalaf and Abdulrahman (2024).

Religions, Islamic Studies scholars Jesper Petersen and Anders Ackfeldt advocate opening up a new field of critical study, of non-Muslim Islams, (Petersen and Ackfeldt 2023) i.e. enunciations of what 'Islam is', or ought to be, by *humans* who *do not* identify as believers in Islam: e.g. ex-Muslim critics, politicians or scholars. Petersen and Ackfeldt argue that there is no *epistemological* reason why scholars should limit their critical analysis to Muslim enunciations. I agree with this, but also claim that recent developments in the field of generative artificial intelligence means that there is similarly no epistemological reason to limit critical analysis to *human* (Muslim or non-Muslim) enunciations. This article is a contribution to such an analysis, within a larger framework of the project *Artificial 'Ulama: Patterns and Biases in non-Human Islam*, funded by Riksbankens Jubileumsfond.

Short on LLMs, biases and hallucinations

At this stage in the article, a very brief introduction to how LLMs work is merited. Put simply, LLMs can be seen as giant prediction engines for natural language. They have been given one task: to predict the next word in a text sequence, considering all the other previous words in that sequence, more specifically, the 'context'. It can be thought of as an autocomplete engine. Technically, the unit for prediction is not actually a word, but something called a 'token', but that detail will be disregarded for the sake of simplicity.

The difference between LLMs and other text autocomplete systems lies in the first 'L'. They are large, incredibly large. The size is a result of the training data, which, at the current state, for the largest models, comprises of virtually everything ever written and available in machine readable form, including, but not limited to, the contents of the Internet. From this training data, the systems construct a multidimensional network in which it arranges all existing words in a giant multilingual vocabulary in relation to one another, called word embeddings, and hence create numerical representations of their meaning. The systems also, by a trial-and-error process over multiple generations, construct highly complex algorithms to determine the probability of all possible words in the vocabulary being the next one, given a preceding word sequence (context). From this basically simple task, unexpected capacities have emerged. Some scholars still prefer to view LLMs as 'mere' next word predictors, as probabilistic autocomplete engines on steroids. (Bender et al. 2021) Others, however, claim that the extensive and large-scale training also gives rise to emergent capabilities of something that in a highly convincing way simulates not only human language,

but also human understanding, human reasoning and human problem solving. (Downes, Forber, and Grzankowski 2024) Currently, the latter position appears to be the more credible. One of the major problems in contemporary AI research is that we do not really know how this is possible. The amount of data processed by the LLMs during training, and the complexity of the algorithms that the system itself produces in the process, are beyond the capacity for human insight and comprehension. We know what the systems are commissioned to do (predict the next word) but we do not know the details of how they arrive at their predictions. Current LLMs are black boxes, and the objects of research within the field of explainable AI. (Rai 2020)

There are two issues concerning LLMs that are important to note for the following. First, LLMs are reliant on their training data. This also means that the character and quality of that data influences their behaviour in terms of the responses they give to a particular request. This raises the question of inherent *biases*, which has been the focus of extensive research. (Navigli, Conia, and Ross 2023; Fulgu and Capraro 2024; Peters 2022) Early models did not perform well in this respect, at times producing output that reflected stereotypes of gender, ethnicity and religion, or even toxic content. Much effort has been put into fine-tuning the models to better align with certain values, (Gabriel 2020) and block them from producing certain content, which in turn have introduced new *biases* towards, for example, values that dominate in the American context in which they (mostly) are produced. (Motoki, Neto, and Rodrigues 2024)

Second, relevant for the following, is that the systems sometimes produce output that is clearly false. This is generally referred to as 'hallucinations' although the use of this term might be seen as undue anthropomorphising. (Ji et al. 2023) The systems have no intention to provide the truth; indeed they have no intention at all, only a task: produce text by predicting the next word, given a particular context. Now, it can be argued that in the case of the systems producing 'non-human Islam' there is no such thing as hallucinations, since, unlike in the world of facts, there is no ground truth in theology. I will, however, claim that in the task of translating the Qur'an, there is, as will be discussed below, some justification for calling the systems out on this.

Procedure

One of the main problems of doing research on LLMs is that they are constantly multiplying and changing. I started to collect and analyse LLM translations in April 2024. The current article was a side project that I worked on

when time allowed. By the time I had a draft ready, in September 2024, new LLMs had been launched, and some of the models I started with had become outdated. I was forced to start a new collection, to add to the data I had already collected, in November and December 2024. Not all 15 models used in this article are available to the public today, and I anticipate that more will disappear before the publication.

I furthermore had to select. I chose models that are well known, accessible to anyone, and generally considered to be top-level. Although autumn 2024 saw the emergence of a new type, called 'reasoning models' I chose not to include any of these. For the task at hand, i.e. translations, there is no indication that these new models are superior to previous ones. I set a definitive end date for including new models to December 31, 2024.

The focus is mainly on large proprietary models in different versions from the dominant AI companies: OpenAI, Anthropic, Google and XAI. Proprietary and 'closed' models are generally more capable than open models (which anyone can download and run locally, provided you have enough computer power). However, for comparison I also included three such open models: two from Meta and one from the French company Mistral. Table 1 displays the models, the companies responsible for training them, and the date or date interval when the translations were collected:

Model	Company	Date of translation (2024)
<i>Proprietary models</i>		
GPT-4o	OpenAI	0514--0516
GPT-4-Turbo	OpenAI	0416--0418
GPT-3.5-Turbo	OpenAI	0415--0416
GPT-4o Mini	OpenAI	1105
Claude 3 Haiku	Anthropic	0317--0404
Claude 3 Sonnet	Anthropic	0418--0419
Claude 3 Opus	Anthropic	0419-0422

Claude 3.5 Sonnet	Anthropic	1104-1105
Grok2	XAI	1222
Gemini 1.5 Pro	Google	1221
Gemini 1.5 Flash	Google	1220
Gemini 2 Flash	Google	1220
<i>Open models</i>		
Mixtral	Mistral AI	0411--0415
Llama 2	Meta	0410--0411
Llama 3	Meta	0424--0425

Table 1: Models used

It is important to note that all models are meant to be general purpose. They have not been specifically fine-tuned for translation tasks, let alone the task of translating the Qur'an. They have been fine-tuned to process any kind of request: i.e. to determine the most powerful Pokémon, to write a poem in the style of Samuel Coleridge or to provide a recipe for hummus.

Method

Prompting is the way in which a user interacts with LLMs, providing instructions for the model to perform a special task.

In the collection of translations, the models were given the same prompt:

```
You are a very able interpreter of the Qur'an. Given
a verse from the Qur'an in Arabic, you will translate
the given verse, and then give your interpretation on
its meaning. Give only one interpretation. Provide
only the interpretation, not a summary of the content
of the verse.
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Additional details were added concerning the exact form of the response that I wanted, but this had to be adjusted for each model, due to differences in their abilities to follow instructions.

The character of the prompt needs some elaboration. First, it specifies a role for the model. It should act as a 'very able translator of the Qur'an'. Hidden in this role is a 'context' that the LLM is implicitly asked to consider, i.e. the religious context of the Qur'an. This frames the translation task. I was not interested in the models' abilities to convert just any Arabic text into English, but in its ability to translate text with a particular cultural significance. If this context had not been provided, it is conceivable that the system would have considered a much larger part of its training data (all Arabic text material). This would not mimic a human Qur'an translator who performs her or his task within an Islamic religious conceptual framework, including previous translations, arguably influencing word choice and style.

The prompt was integrated into a script in Python code that sent requests to the models, one verse at a time, using so-called APIs (Application Programming Interface). For the proprietary models, I used the official APIs of OpenAI, Anthropic, Google and X. The open-source models were accessed using the API of the cloud service Groq. The open models could be queried for free, while the closed models incurred some costs, all in all approximately 50 US dollars.

I used a version of the Arabic text of the Qur'an without vowels, downloaded from the translation repository tanzil.net. This merits some comments. Just as I did not want the models to use all Arabic training data for the translation task, through providing information that the text to translate was from the Qur'an, I deliberately wanted the models to engage in genuine translation rather than merely reproducing memorized connections between Arabic text segments and their English equivalents. By using unvoweled Arabic text, which likely differs from most examples in their training data, I encouraged the LLMs to translate the meaning of the text instead of simply retrieving pre-existing translations. If I had provided an Arabic text with vowels, which is presumably relatively uncommon in the training data, the risk was that existing training material with parallel renderings of Arabic and English (i.e. English translation of the Qur'an) would unduly influence the output.

While the responses from the models, in line with the prompt, contained both the translation and a *tafsīr*, I here focus only on the former. An analysis of LLM interpretations of Qur'anic verses (beyond the interpretation possibly inherent in the translation), will be reserved for later studies.

The models were prompted to provide translations on a verse-by-verse basis. Already at this stage, there is perhaps a significant difference compared to how

humans would approach the same translation task. Most human translators will, and perhaps rightly so, claim that any correct translation of a particular Qur'anic verse needs considering the context of surrounding verses, the Sura in which the verse appears, the larger context of the Qur'an as a whole, its religious 'worldview', or its socio-historical context, or all of these in combination. Neither is *explicitly* given as context in the prompt above. However, considering how the LLMs are trained, it could be suspected that such contexts as those mentioned, are to some degree already present in the models' interior representations, and activated by providing the information that the text is indeed from the Qur'an.

The translation task was performed only once per model. One of the peculiarities of LLMs is that their output is often unpredictable. The same prompt can produce different outputs, over consecutive attempts, since the next token prediction is probabilistic. Furthermore, there is the possibility for adjustments of the level of 'creativity' (called temperature) the LLM is allowed in its response, in practice 'choosing' between different next words and not merely picking the most probable one. In principle, I could have produced many translations for each of the models, with different 'temperature' settings. I, however, chose not to, due to time and cost constraints. I used the default temperature setting.

Unlike in the case of *sureQuran*, there was no human-in-the-loop in compiling the translations. I just collected what the systems delivered, without redaction. The only interference from my side was to, in a few cases, rerun the script if there was an error. Almost all models did succeed with the task, at the first go, with some notable exceptions. All three Gemini models returned an error message for some verses, of a kind not encountered in any other model. They refused output citing potential copyright infringements. This indicates a fine tuning, or possibly a control instance against the web, not to reproduce already existing translations verbatim. The number of such refusals could be reduced by consecutive requests. Gemini 2 Flash first refused to translate 90 verses, but after prompting the model ten times (before giving up), the number of refusals was reduced to four (Q 2:168, Q 7:155, Q 23:117 and Q 33:5). Gemini 1.5 Pro still refused one verse after ten attempts (Q 6:19). Gemini 1.5 Flash's initial refusals could all be rectified in three attempts.

The dataset is available for download (Svensson 2026) but also as an interactive application (<https://llmtranslnt.streamlit.app>)

Example: Sura 112

Comparative studies of Qur'an translations are hard work, which makes most previous attempts in the research area limited in scope. They usually focus for example on a restricted set of topics, or restricted set of verses, or recurring stylistic patterns. The emergence of computer assisted methods has made more large-scale comparative work possible, but the methods have often been crude and the results tentative at best. (see e.g. Al Ghamdi 2015) With the advent of generative AI, however, this has been somewhat redeemed, as will be shown below. Even so, there is of course no space in this article for a full, detailed, verse by verse, comparison of the LLM translations. Still, it is justified to provide an example of the results, with some general comments. I here choose *sura* 112, *al-Ikhlāṣ* which is both short and well known to any scholar in Islamic studies. This is meant only as an illustration and should not be seen as representative of LLM translations of the entire Qur'an. The different LLM translations of the chapter are given in Appendix I.

One can note that there are no two identical LLM translations of Q 112, although there are individual verses that are identical in two or more translations. A noteworthy difference between the highly similar translations is that some, in Q 112:1, display the recurring tendency in human translations to use explanatory interjections between brackets ('[who is]'). Claude Sonnet, alone, introduces an extra theological emphasis (without brackets) on the nature of the concept of *tawḥīd*, divine unity, when adding 'and only' after 'one', which is not explicit, but perhaps theologically implicit, in the verse. One can also note that most translations use 'Allah' and not 'God' to render the Arabic word *allāh*, except the translations by GPT4o-Mini and Google Gemini Flash who, inconsistently, use both. Which word to use is an issue of ongoing controversy among *human* translations, (Hassen 2010) and in *sureQuran*, the user can choose either from a drop-down window. From the result here, however, it would be reasonable to assume that Allah is dominant in the training data, i.e. translations available in digital form. This is a first indication on how the output from LLM translations may provide interesting, general results, in this case whether human Qur'an translators, at least those available in machine readable format, prefer 'Allah' or 'God'.

Examples of hallucinations are found in the three open, and less capable, models: Llama2, Llama 3 and Mixtral. Llama 2's hallucination in verse 2, which appears to be rather a translation of either Q 7:4 or Q 20:58 is actually common overall in that model, occurring as the 'translation' of 826 verses. It is also present as a hallucination in a few verses in both the Llama 3 and Mixtral translation.

Why this is so is opaque. It could be a result of the verse appearing often in the training data. But it could also be a result of the instruct tuning process, where the model is 'taught' how to perform certain tasks. The data for such finetuning is in the form of a large dataset of inputs, with the desired outputs (created by humans or machines). It is hence possible that the translations of verse 7:4 or verse 20:58 were used as examples of the task of 'Qur'an translation'. I would hold this more likely, since the overrepresentation of this particular 'translation' is limited to one model.

The Llama 2's hallucination in Q 112:3 matches Q 21:16, Q 38:27 and Q 44:38, but occurs only once. Interestingly enough, all three hallucinating models return a similar, *but not identical* hallucination in the last verse of the sura. The translation appears to be more suitable for Q 18:43. One reason for this particular hallucination can be that the 'autocomplete' function takes over. Both verses start in a similar manner '*Wa lam yakun lahu*' (Q 112:4) and '*Wa lam takun lahu*' (Q 18:43). It is possible that the prediction engine here overrides parts of the provided context (the Arabic text) after the initial 'wa lam'. What is important to note, however, is that the hallucinations are all within a Qur'anic framework, i.e. the models do not hallucinate just any random phrase in Arabic.

Similarity with existing human translations

Comparing LLM translation to one another may, however, not be that interesting. More interesting is how they relate to existing human translations. There are currently over a hundred translations of the Qur'an into English (now expanded with 15). Many of these are available in digital form online, and have thus most likely been part of the LLM training data, scraped off the Internet. In addition to full translations, the training data most probably contained instances of Qur'an translations being quoted in general discourses on Islam on the Internet. But which translations?

To answer this question I opted for a conceptually simple but at the same time for the task sufficient, similarity-measuring procedure: the Jaccard similarity which measures lexical similarity between two texts. This is done by calculating the ratio between the number of unique shared words and the sum of unique words contained in both texts. The resulting figure ranges between 0 similarity (no shared words) to 1.0 similarity (all words shared). An example from verse 112:1:

GPT4o: 'And there is none comparable to Him'

Llama2: 'And he had no one to help him.'

Shared unique tokens=3 ('and', 'to', 'him')

Total unique tokens=12 ('and', 'there', 'is', 'none', 'comparable', 'to', 'him', 'he', 'had', 'no', 'one', 'help')

Jaccard similarity = $3/12=0.25$.

Since the question, at least in the current stage, concerns to which extent the LLMs reproduce words in existing human Qur'an translations the Jaccard index is sufficient. A large, relative overlap of words between an LLM translation and a particular human translation indicates that the latter played a significant part in the training data of the former.

Before venturing into that issue, however, a quick note could be made of the internal similarity between the LLM translations. In the case of Sura 112, the translations are quite similar, but with a few differences, for example the translation of *al-ṣamad*, in verse 2 as 'Eternal', 'Eternal Refuge' or 'Self-Sufficient'. All alternatives exist in human translations (cf. online collections such as tanzil.net, quran.com or islamawakened.com). A few remarks can be made. The two models Claude Opus and GPT3 has the largest Jaccard similarity of 0.75. The models Llama2 and Mixtral both have low Jaccard similarity with the others. The average Jaccard similarity for all translations is 0.62.

This figure says very little. For an earlier project, I collected and compared the Jaccard similarity between 51 examples of human translations of the Qur'an all available on the Internet. (Svensson 2019) The average Jaccard similarity for all translations was 0.36. So, considering only the words used, the LLM translations are more similar to one another than human translations are.

The mean Jaccard similarity score between each LLM translation and the available human translations range between 0.40 (Llama2) and 0.46 (Claude Sonnet 3.5). But similarities are not equally distributed. The lowest mean Jaccard similarity (0.33) of all LLM translation and a particular human translation is with the rather odd *Al-Muntakhab*, published in 1980. This makes sense. Strictly speaking, this is not a translation from the Arabic text of the Qur'an, but a translation of a *tafsīr* into colloquial Arabic, a somewhat failed attempt from Egypt to compete with Saudi Arabia in global *da'wa* through Qur'an translations. (Saeed 2020; Wild 2015, 48)

The highest overall *mean* similarity score (0.64), however, is perhaps less anticipated. It is with the translation *Sahih International*. This translation scores the highest similarity with all LLM translations. Claude Opus is here the LLM with the highest Jaccard similarity, 0.84. The one with the lowest is Llama2, 0.47, which however is still above the mean in the overall comparison between LLM translations and human translations. Why this high level of similarity with this translation across the LLMs?

The *Sahih International*, first published in 1997, is widely used in contemporary English-speaking contexts. It was produced by three American female converts to Islam: Umm Muhammad (Emily Assami), Mary Kennedy, and Amatullah Bantley. (Zavadski 2017, 3; Yakubovych 2024b) The use of the term 'Sahih', i.e. 'authentic' or 'sound', indicates that the translators viewed their work as somewhat different from other translations in terms of keeping close to the original text. There has been some criticism of the translation, perhaps more due to the context of its production, than to a detailed assessment of content. It is generally considered to be more conservative, and Salafi oriented, with a definitive Sunni orthodox bias. It was originally published by the Saudi Arabian Dar Abul Qasim, a publishing house in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia, but has been republished in many editions by several publishers, as well made public in digital form on several websites.

The latter fact is then the obvious answer to the question why. The high level of similarity is simply a result of an overrepresentation in the training data. Digital versions of *Sahih International* are readily available for download, but also, most probably given its widespread use, it is quoted in many contexts: on homepages, in English e-fatwas, in Muslim discussion groups etc. Katie Zavadski's somewhat anecdotal (since it is most likely not based on extensive quantitative research) claim that *Sahih International* is 'frequently the default translation on religious websites' (Zavadski 2017, 9) becomes highly likely in the light of these results.

Still, however, it is important to note that none of the LLM translations display a Jaccard similarity of 1.0 with *Sahih International*. It is then not a matter of the LLMs having stored that particular translation in memory and retrieving it upon being prompted to 'translate'. That is not how LLMs work. A more conceivable explanation is that in LLM's selecting the next most probable word in a sequence translating a verse from the Qur'an, a word in *Sahih International* is more likely to be chosen, due to its presence in the training data. But LLMs are not fully deterministic, which accounts for the divergence.

Furthermore, translations of the Qur'an are not the sole relevant training data. So is everything written in Arabic. This indicates, another, but less likely, possible explanation for a large lexical overlap between LLMs and *Sahih International*: The translators of the former explicitly attempted to stay close to the source text. Interviewed by Zavadski, religious studies scholar Bruce Lawrence, who has written a valuable overview on Qur'an translations into English, (Lawrence 2017) does not hold *Sahih International* as a favorite, claiming that it 'hammers the language, it does not make it sing'. (Zavadski 2017, 9) It does not have the aesthetic value, perhaps, of a more poetic, and less literal, translation. Could it then be that the high Jaccard similarity between the LLM translations and *Sahih International* is merely a result of them both using more literal renderings of the words in the Arabic source text? To answer that question, there is need for a less crude method for measuring similarity than the Jaccard index.

Similarity and differences on a verse level

To answer more detailed questions on the LLM translations' reliance on *Sahih International* one needs to make a comparison on verse level. Such a comparison lies clearly beyond the scope of the current article. Suggesting a method through which it could be done, however, is not. This means a slight shift away from the issue of LLMs as objects of study, to LLMs as tools for analysis in comparative studies in Qur'an translations.

As mentioned above, there is previous research that compares translations of the Qur'an. Most are from a 'top-down' perspective, approaching translations with a particular set of ideas or hypotheses concerning in which parts of the text similarities and differences can be expected. I here, instead, suggest a 'bottom-up' method, where each and every verse pair in two translations is scanned for similarities and differences. It is understandable that such an inductive method has seldom been used in previous research. It would be too time consuming.

LLMs do bring about a change here. As part of their training, LLMs encode meaning of words and therefore also of word sequences. This can be utilized in research.

Short on sentence embeddings and semantic comparison

Sentence embeddings is a recent technique that utilizes pretrained LLMs to organize text units based on their semantic similarity. In simplified terms, the LLM 'reads' a piece of text, and gives it a position in a multidimensional vector

space based on its semantic content. The semantic similarity between two 'read' and positioned pieces of texts can then be determined by their proximity in this multidimensional vector space. (Sun et al. 2022, 598) This is a powerful technology compared to previous methods of determining text similarity, including the lexically based method for arriving at a Jaccard similarity used above.

The power of the technology is best displayed through some examples. Below, the widely used text embedding pre-trained model 'all-MiniLM-L6-v2' has been employed to determine the similarity between six text pairs. The result is displayed in table 2. As in the case of the Jaccard index, the score ranges between 0 (no similarity) to 1 (identical). Examples 1 and 2 have been made up, but the rest are taken from actual LLM translations of Q 112 above.

	Text pairs	Similarity
1.	a. Allah, the Eternal b. God has always existed	0.55
2.	a. Allah, the Eternal created heaven and the earth b. God has always existed and made the heaven and the earth	0.67
3.	a. He neither begets nor is born b. He neither begets nor is He begotten	0.86
4.	a. And there is none comparable unto Him b. And there was not for Him any equal	0.62
5.	a. And he had no helper at all b. And there is none comparable to Him	0.40
6.	a. He neither begets nor is born b. And indeed, We have not created the heavens and the earth and what is between them except in truth and not for amusement	0.22

Table 2: Text similarity using sentence embeddings

To a human reader, the phrases in example 1 convey a similar, but perhaps not identical, meaning. If one would calculate their Jaccard similarity, the phrases would have a similarity score of exactly 0, since they do not share any words.

When compared using sentence-transformers, however, they do receive a similarity score of 0.55.

Exactly what the number 0.55 represents is opaque, but the algorithm does appear to account for both the fact that the sentences are semantically quite similar, and lexically totally dissimilar. An indication of this is case 2, where some words are added to increase the number of shared words. The similarity score increases. In case 3, the two phrases are semantically equivalent, but lexically slightly different, and the similarity score is even higher. Case 4 and 5 show what happens if one introduces semantic variation, also taken from the translations above. Example 6 shows the score when comparing a translation with an obvious hallucination. It is important to note that the similarity score here is not 0. It is impossible to know what 0.22 here 'means'. I would argue that it is only in a *relational* and not *absolute* sense that these figures have meaning. But relative is what is needed in the context of the present article.

If one uses sentence-transformers and compares verse by verse each of the LLM translations with my online version of *Sahih International*, downloaded from *tanzil.net*,³ one arrives at the following mean similarity for all verse pairs. Each comparison between an LLM translation and *Sahih International*, using the Python library Sentence Transformer, and the model 'all-MiniLM-L6-v2' took around eight minutes.

Model	Mean similarity with <i>Sahih International</i>
GPT3	0.86
GPT4	0.85
GPT4o	0.89
GPT4mini	0.84
Gemini 1.5 flash	0.77
Gemini 1.5 pro	0.85

³ It should be noted that Swedish law, since being aligned with the EU Copyright Directive, allows the author as a researcher to store and use for data mining any copyrighted material to which legal access exists. The corpus of digitised Qur'an translations used for comparative purposes in this article has been stored securely and is not accessible to anyone else.

Model	Mean similarity with <i>Sahih International</i>
Gemini 2.0 flash	0.87
Claude Opus	0.92
Claude Sonnet	0.85
Claude Haiku	0.87
Claude Sonnet 3.5	0.88
Grok2	0.85
Llama2	0.54
Llama3	0.79
Mixtral	0.72

Table 3: Verse-level mean semantic similarity between LLM and Sahih International translations

The results are similar to the comparison using the Jaccard index above, in the sense that it is the commercial, 'closed', models that have the highest mean score. The top scorers belong to what is at the time or writing considered to be two of the top performance models: GPT4o and Claude Opus. In the following, I will focus on these two top scorers when I now proceed to a verse-by-verse comparison.

GPT4o, Claude Opus and Sahih International: Some verse level comparisons

As can be seen from table 2, the mean similarity score was 0.89 for GPT4o and 0.92 for Claude Opus. This would indicate a high level of general similarity. But how similar are the translations of individual verses?

The number of identical verse translations, between GPT4o and *Sahih International*, i.e. with a similarity score of 1.0 is 602, i.e. approximately 10% of the total. In the case of Opus, however, the number of identical verses is much larger, 2085, which is almost exactly a third. With the exception of GPT3 (11%) and Claude Haiku (10%), the other LLMs have a lower overlap of identical verses with *Sahih International*, ranging between 0.5 and 6%.

Now, we can return to the issue raised by Pink above. In a sense, Pink is correct when claiming that LLMs are parasitic on 'countless of human translators' of the Qur'an, but there may be differences between models here. Given the evidence, it would seem difficult for OpenAI and Anthropic, and particularly the latter, to claim that the outputs their models produce are not, to a large extent, reproducing the work of others. However, the plagiarism is not intentional, it is a byproduct of a training that is largely unsupervised, and hence beyond human control. It is not as if a human translator, willfully, had copied a translation of a verse from another translator. OpenAI and Anthropic have not purposely fed the models with a large quantity of copies of *Sahih International*. It is humans that, for quite some time and probably to a large extent, have put copies of or excerpts from *Sahih International* online, for everyone, including automatic web crawlers, to read. That the models have been trained on copyrighted material is a direct result of such copyrighted material having been made easily available to everyone.⁴

Even when there is a large percentage of verses that are identical, especially in the case of Claude Opus, there is still reason to probe further into what similarity scores below 1.0 mean. Appendix II and Appendix III provide sets of example pairs between Opus' and GPT4o's translations and *Sahih International*, with similarity scores below 1.0. Each example is the verse pair that scored the top similarity value in intervals of 0.05 from values below 1.0. I will use these examples to provide some general remarks presently. But first I would like to point to the two translation pairs in each comparison with the lowest scores.

For GPT4o it is the following two verses:

Verse	GPT4o	Sahih international	Similarity
53:56	This is a warning like the former warnings.	This [Prophet] is a warner like the former warners	0.18
74.42	What has caused you to enter Hell?	[And asking them], "What put you into Saqar?"	0.18

Table 4: Comparison GPT4o and Sahih International

⁴ For a comparable example with the Harry Potter books, see Eldan and Russinovich (2023).

In the case of Q 53:56 the two translations do deviate in meaning, between translating the Arabic *nadhīr* as 'warning' or as 'warner', and the plural *nudhuri*, as 'warnings' and 'warners'. Both are linguistically possible, and both occur in human translations. In another context, (Q 74:36) *Sahih International* does translate *nadhīr* as 'warning'. Albeit these are translations with clearly different meanings, neither can be said to be more correct than the other. In Q 74.42 GPT4o follows the majority of human translations in translating *saqar* as 'hell', or similar. In Islamic theological tradition, *saqar*, refers to one of the levels in hell. The words provided between hard brackets in the *Sahih International* translation are not in the Arabic text, so here GPT4o conforms more with the original. It could be argued that the difference between the two translations in rendering the word *salakakum* in Q 74:42 as either 'caused you to enter' or 'put you into' is minor, but the former is again, arguably and following Lane, a slightly more literal rendering of the root verb *salaka*. (Lane 1863, 1424)

In the case of Claude Opus, the two verses with the lowest similarity are the following:

Verse	Claude Opus	Sahih international	Similarity
88:3	Amilatun Nasibatun	Working [hard] and exhausted	0.11
75:25	You think that he would do with it poverty	Expecting that there will be done to them [something] backbreaking.	0.08

Table 5: Comparison Claude Opus and Sahih International

Q 88:3 is an obvious mistake where Opus transliterates instead of translates. Q 75:25 would appear to be a hallucination, because it does not really make sense. However, it should be remembered that the Arabic text used does not contain vowels and does not have context. Without the vowels, the first-person form of the verb 'to do', *fa'ala*, could be interpreted both as passive and active. 'To them' in the *Sahih International* translation refers to 'faces' in the previous verse, using the collective feminine pronoun *-ha*, which without this context could just as well be translated as 'her' or 'it'. The word *faqira*, is a technical term for a 'backbreaking' catastrophic event or calamity, (Lane 1863, 2425) but the root f-q-r does have connotations to poverty. So, while Claude Opus' translation is difficult to comprehend, it is not an outright hallucination, but rather a creative act of

making sense of the Arabic text provided without context. It can be noted that ten out of the fifteen LLM translations here deviate substantially from the *Sahih International* translation. All the human translations that I have consulted are more in line with it. This again illustrates that the artificial systems' approach to translating the Qur'an is not one of merely sampling from existing translations.

For the rest of the verses that fall short of being identical, similar close comparisons could be made. It could be argued that the main benefit of using the method suggested here, however, not only for the current task, but for all similar attempts at a bottom-up comparison, is to be able to exclude verses less worthy of attention. Looking more closely at appendices 2 and 3, it would be possible to set a reasonable dividing line. Where exactly the threshold should be set is, however, quite subjective and problem-specific.

In my judgement, verse pairs with a similarity score above 0.95 appear as good as identical in both cases. If so, the percentage of verse translations identical with verse translations in *Sahih International* is raised to 65 percent for Claude Opus and 46 percent for GPT4o. Below the level of 0.95 there are changes in wording that are less significant, but below around 0.75 in both cases, slight semantic differences begin to appear. If 0.75 is set as the upper limit, this leaves a total of 636 verses in the Opus case, and 830 in the GPT4o case. These numbers are still fairly large for manual processing, but a considerable reduction compared to the total of 6235.

Although I will not be performing a full-scale comparison here, one can note some possible patterns that emerge for the examples of translation pairs with a similarity score below 0.75.

In Q 75:16, GPT4o delivers a translation that is close to the Arabic original. *Sahih International*, on the other hand, inserts, between brackets, an interpretation of the 'it' mentioned in the verse, and in the following verses, as referring to 'the Qur'an'. Such an insertion mirrors a particular understanding of the historical context, i.e. that there at the time existed a Qur'an to be recited from, which may be contested. Interpretations may also be inserted without brackets, as in the case of Q 74:39 where *Sahih International* invokes a technical term 'the companions of the right' from theological tradition, denoting a separate, privileged, group among the believers (as indicated in Q 56:8-9). GPT4o here does not provide a response that attaches to this wider Qur'anic context, and the theological tradition, but rather points to a more literal understanding of the verse (people located on the right hand side). Lastly, in verse 98:3, there is a subtle difference that may point

to the Salafi orientation of *Sahih International* claimed in previous research. The difference here lies in the translation of the adjective *qaymiyya* as either 'valuable' or 'correct'. Both exist in previous human translations. Here there might be a subtle difference between either viewing the scriptures in question as inherently valuable or viewing them as important because they contain certain information. An explanatory insertion for the adjective 'correct' in my printed version of *Sahih International* (not present in the online versions that I have consulted) may provide a clue as to the understanding of wherein the value lies: '[i.e. regulations and laws]'. (Saheeh International 2012, 644)

In the case of Opus' translation, one can note that the method of sentence embeddings may be used to spot hallucinations, as in verse 74:29, where the Opus translation has no direct correspondence in the Qur'an, let alone being a translation of the verse in question. However, the root of the verb *her* understood as 'burning' or 'scorching' in most human translations, does share the root l-w-h with the word for 'tablet', as in *al-lawh al-mahfuz* referring to the 'heavenly tablet' (Q 85:22). In the translation of Q 80:17 there is again a difference that can be attributed to the fact that the Arabic text given to Opus to translate lacks vowels, translating the verb 'to kill', *qatala*, in an active, and not passive form, the latter understood metaphorically in the *Sahih International* translation. Again, this is evidence that the LLM translation is not always a reproduction or sampling of existing, human, translations but can also be a constructive process. As in the case of *Sahih International* vs GPT4o, there is a possible difference attributable to a Salafi leaning in the *Sahih International* translation of Q 30:13. Opus translates the word *shurakā'* as *beings* associated 'with Allah'. This is not explicit in the original, but (possibly) implicit in it. Several human translations do specify that the term denotes association with Allah. But not *Sahih International*. The more literal translation, 'their partners', allows for a wider understanding, potentially including also human intercessors, in line with a Salafi understanding of what constitutes the grave sin of *shirk*.

Concluding remarks

This article constitutes, as far as I know, the first attempt at a larger comparative analysis of Qur'an translations made by LLMs. The models prompted with verses in Arabic and asked to act in a role of professional Qur'an translators have produced 15 new English translations. Admittedly, Pink's statement that these are parasitic of human translations holds true, at least to some extent. It is clear that the results show a predominance particularly for one such human

translation, that of *Sahih International*, and the reliance on this particular translation as training data is most evident in the most capable models.

A significant limitation in this analysis must be acknowledged, however, regarding the opacity of LLM training data. Commercial AI companies rarely disclose comprehensive details about their training datasets, particularly regarding which specific texts were included and their relative proportions. While we can reasonably assume that widely available online translations of the Qur'an were included in the training data, we cannot know with certainty which translations were represented, in what proportions, or how they were processed during training. This creates an inherent 'black box' problem that complicates the interpretation of the findings presented here. The patterns of similarity identified between LLM outputs and existing translations offer strong circumstantial evidence of training data composition, but cannot be considered definitive proof of specific training methodologies or data sources.

At the same time, looking more closely at Claude Opus' and GPT4o's translations, one can note cases where the LLMs in question do not merely reproduce the content of previous translations, but produce something that is more creative, perhaps unique. Some are clearly hallucinations, but not all.

We see indications above of possible conflicting contexts for the models: the context of the Qur'an, steering the model towards reproducing text in the human translations in the training data, and the context of Arabic, steering the models towards performing a more general translation. This, then, merits a qualification of Pink's critique. In some respects, the models are clearly using the 'work of countless human translators', to the extent that their work has been made public on the Internet. However, the models also use all other texts thus available, or rather they use the patterns inherent in those texts. In this sense, it could be argued that the models in a sense mimic the work of human translators. It is conceivable that most human translators, when embarking on the task to provide a new English translation of the Qur'an, will have more than one glance at previous translations when determining which word to select next. There may be a thin line between plagiarism and inspiration.

It must here be remembered that I used default settings for 'temperature'. If this had been raised, it is possible, even likely, that GPT4o and Claude Opus would have deviated more from the text in *Sahih International*. This may be explored further in future research. Such research may address not only if a change in temperature lessens the similarity with *Sahih International*, but also

what a higher level of 'creativity' (that is larger freedom to select from a wider range of most likely next tokens) will entail for the translations as such. Similar experiments, exploring the creativity of the models could include asking for translations that rhyme, or asking for translations that mimic the style of some specific text or poet. A perhaps more interesting manipulation, from the point of Islamic studies, would be to provide the model with a specific role. The prompt used consistently in the communication with the models did limit that role to a 'very able interpreter of the Qur'an', with no further specification. This can be adjusted to cater for a particular religious or ideological leaning: traditional, feminist, sufi, islamophobic etc, to explore what 'knowledge' (or stereotypes) of such contemporary or historical positions resides in the models. Considering the time and cost, however, such experiments of creativity manipulations and role play may be more suitable to perform iteratively with a more limited set of verses, than with the whole of the Qur'anic text.

The overall dominance for *Sahih International* in providing 'inspiration' (or training material) for the LLM may be cause for concern for some Muslims, given the strong association with Saudi Arabian *da'wa* initiatives, and consequently with Salafism as a version of Islam in contemporary conflict with other versions. However, to which extent this particular translation does contain a clear Salafi bias is still a question that needs to be answered by a more detailed comparative approach. The bottom-up method suggested for the comparative study of Qur'an translations in this article may be a way to achieve that.

This study has demonstrated that LLM translations of the Qur'an represent a complex interplay between reproduction and innovation. While these models clearly draw heavily from existing translations—particularly the *Sahih International* translation—they also exhibit creative capacities when confronted with ambiguous text or contextual challenges. This technological development raises profound questions not only about copyright and intellectual attribution but also about the very nature of translation itself. If we understand translation as an interpretive act that reflects the translator's worldview, what does it mean when this act is performed by a system without conscious intention yet trained on human cultural products? The emergence of LLM translations thus invites us to reconsider the boundaries between human and machine creativity in the context of sacred texts.

Looking ahead, the implications of this development extend far beyond academic interest. As LLM technologies become increasingly integrated into everyday digital experiences, they will likely become the primary mediators

through which many non-Arabic speakers encounter the Qur'an. This shift also affects Muslim communities worldwide, who must grapple with whether and how to incorporate these technologies into religious practice and education, and what the effects of such incorporations are on issues such as religious authority and scholarship. Further research in this area will be essential as we enter an era where artificial intelligence increasingly shapes our understanding of and access to religious traditions.

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Appendix 1. LLM translations of Sura 112, *al-Ikhlās*

Open AI models

GPT3	GPT4turbo	GPT4o	GPT4o-Mini
1. Say, "He is Allah, [who is] One", 2. Allah, the Eternal Refuge. 3. He neither begets nor is born. 4. And there is none comparable unto Him.	1. Say, He is Allah, [Who is] One 2. Allah, the Eternal 3. He neither begets nor is born 4. And there is none comparable to Him.	1. Say, He is Allah, [who is] One. 2. Allah, the Eternal Refuge 3. He neither begets nor is born 4. And there is none comparable to Him.	1. Say, 'He is Allah, [who is] One, 2. God, the Eternal Refuge. 3. He neither begets nor is born. 4. And there is none comparable to Him.

Anthropic models

Opus	Sonnet	Haiku	Sonnet 3.5
1. Say: He is Allah, the One. 2. Allah, the Eternal, Absolute 4. He neither begets nor is born, 5. And there is none comparable to Him.	1. Say, 'He is Allah, the One and Only' 2. Allah, the Self-Sufficient 3. He neither begets nor is born 4. And there was not for Him any equal	1, Say, "He is Allah, [who is] One", 2. Allah, the Self-Sufficient 3. He neither begets nor is He begotten 4. And there is none comparable to Him.	1. Say, "He is Allah, [who is] One" 2. Allah, the Eternal, the Absolute 3. He begets not, nor was He begotten 4. And there is none comparable to Him

Google models

Gemini Pro	Gemini 1.5 Flash	Gemini 2.0 Flash
1. Say, "He is Allah, [who is] One," 2. Allah, the Eternal Refuge. 3. He neither begets nor is begotten. 4. And there is nothing like unto Him.	1. Say, 'He is God, the One'. 2. Allah, the Eternal Refuge. 3. He has neither begotten, nor been begotten. 4. And no one is equal to Him.	1. Say, "He is Allah, [who is] One." 2. Allah, the Eternal Refuge. 3. He begets not, nor was He begotten. 4. And there is none comparable to Him.

XAI model

Grok 2
1. Say, He is Allah, the One. 2. Allah, the Eternal Refuge 3. He begets not, nor was He begotten 4. And there is none like unto Him.

Open models

Llama2 (Meta)	Llama3 (Meta)	Mixtral (Mistral)
1. Say, 'He is Allah, [who is] One', 2. And how many a town have We destroyed while it was unjust, so Our punishment came to it in the morning, or at noon. 3. And indeed, We have not created the heavens and the earth and what is between them except in truth and not for amusement. 4. And he had no one to help him.	1. He is Allah, [who is] One. 2. Allah, the Self-Sufficient 3. He begets not, nor was He begotten. 4. And he had no helper at all.	1. Say, 'He is Allah, [who is] One' 2. Allah, the Eternal 3. has not begotten nor was begotten 4. And he had no strength to help himself.

Appendix 2. Comparison GPT4o-Sahih

Range	Number	Verse	Example		Score
			GPT4o	Sahih International	
0.95-0.99	2128	11:58	And when Our command came, We saved Hud and those who believed with him by mercy from Us; and We saved them from a harsh punishment.	And when Our command came, We saved Hud and those who believed with him, by mercy from Us; and We saved them from a harsh punishment.	0.999
		5:112	When the disciples said, "O Jesus, son of Mary, can your Lord send down to us a table spread with food from heaven?" Jesus said, "Fear Allah, if you should be believers."	And remember] when the disciples said, "O Jesus, Son of Mary, can your Lord send down to us a table [spread with food] from the heaven? [Jesus] said," Fear Allah , if you should be believers."	0.95
0.90-0.95	973	13:30	Thus We have sent you to a community before which other communities have passed away, to recite to them what We have revealed to you while they disbelieve in the Most Merciful. Say, 'He is my Lord; there is no deity except Him. In Him I have put my trust, and to Him is my return.'	Thus have We sent you to a community before which [other] communities have passed on so you might recite to them that which We revealed to you, while they disbelieve in the Most Merciful. Say, "He is my Lord; there is no deity except Him. Upon Him I rely, and to Him is my return."	0.90
0.85-0.90	663	26:85	And make me among the inheritors of the Garden of Delight.	And place me among the inheritors of the Garden of Pleasure.	0.85
0.80-0.85	514	9:71	The believers, men and women, are protectors of one another. They enjoin what is right and forbid what is wrong. They observe regular prayers, give charity (zakat), and obey Allah and His Messenger. Allah will have mercy on them. Indeed, Allah is Exalted in Might and Wise.	The believing men and believing women are allies of one another. They enjoin what is right and forbid what is wrong and establish prayer and give zakah and obey Allah and His Messenger. Those - Allah will have mercy upon them. Indeed, Allah is Exalted in Might and Wise.	0.80
0.75-0.80	379	9:76	But when He gave them out of His grace, they were stingy with it and turned away, evading (their duties).	But when he gave them from His bounty, they were stingy with it and turned away while they refused.	0.75
0.70-0.75	260	70:37	on the right and on the left, in separate groups	[To sit] on [your] right and [your] left in separate groups?	0.70
0.65-0.70	201	89:4	By the night as it departs	And [by] the night when it passes,	0.65
0.60- 0.65	130	75:16	Do not move your tongue with it to hasten with it.	Move not your tongue with it, [O Muhammad], to hasten with it [i.e. recitation of the Qur'an].	0.60
0.55-0.60	82	56:42	In scorching wind and scalding water	[They will be] in scorching fire and scalding water	0.55
0.50-0.55	54	74:39	Except for those on the right hand	Except the companions of the right,	0.50
0.45-0.50	42	36:24	Indeed, I am in clear error. :	Indeed, I would then be in manifest error.	0.45
0.40-0.45	26	100:5	Then rushed into the midst of the gathering	Arriving thereby in the center collectively,	0.40
0.35-0.40	17	79:2	And those who glide smoothly.	And [by] those who remove with ease	0.35
0.30-0.35	10	98:3	Therein are valuable scriptures	Within which are correct writings.	0.30
0.25-0.30	6	17:14	Read your book; your soul suffices today as your own reckoner.	[It will be said], "Read your record. Sufficient is yourself against you this Day as accountant."	0.25
0.20-0.25	2	51:10	Accursed are the liars	Destroyed are the falsifiers	0.23

Appendix 3. Comparison Opus-Sahih

Range	Number	Examples (top similarity score in each interval)			
		Verse	Opus	Sahih	Score
0.95-<1	1975	27:49	They said, "Take a mutual oath by Allah that we will kill him by night, him and his family. Then we will say to his executor, 'We did not witness the destruction of his family, and indeed, we are truthful.'"	They said, "Take a mutual oath by Allah that we will kill him by night, he and his family. Then we will say to his executor, 'We did not witness the destruction of his family, and indeed, we are truthful.' "	0.999..
		23:59	And those who do not associate anything with their Lord.	And they who do not associate anything with their Lord	0.95
0.90-0.95	558	37:112	And We gave him the good news of Isaac, a prophet from among the righteous.	And We gave him good tidings of Isaac, a prophet from among the righteous.	0.90
0.85-0.90	394	73:7	Verily, you have by day prolonged occupation.	Indeed, for you by day is prolonged occupation.	0.85
0.80-0.85	323	84:9	And he will return to his people in joy.	And return to his people in happiness.	0.80
0.75-0.80	263	21:99	If these were gods, they would not have entered it, and all of them will abide therein eternally.	Had these [false deities] been [actual] gods, they would not have come to it, but all are eternal therein.	0.75
0.70-0.75	193	26:54	Indeed, those are but a small band.	[And said], "Indeed, those are but a small band,	0.70
0.65-0.70	133	88:4	He will burn in a Flaming Fire.	They will [enter to] burn in an intensely hot Fire.	0.65
0.60- 0.65	106	69:27	Oh, would that it had been the decisive one.	I wish it my death had been the decisive one. *	0.60
0.55-0.60	54	30:13	And those they associate with Allah will not intercede for them, and they will deny their association.	And there will not be for them among their [alleged] partners any intercessors, and they will [then] be disbelievers in their partners.	0.55
0.50-0.55	53	82:9	No! But you deny the Judgment.	No! But you deny the Recompense.	0.50
0.45-0.50	28	107:7	And refuse [to give] small kindnesses.	And withhold [simple] assistance.	0.45
0.40-0.45	28	56:89	So [they will be] among gardens and springs	Then [for him is] rest and bounty and a garden of pleasure.	0.40
0.35-0.40	13	80:17	Man has killed, how ungrateful he is!	Cursed is man; how disbelieving is he.	0.35
0.30-0.35	12	51:9	Averted from it [i.e., the Fire] will be he who was the most righteous.	Deluded away from the Qur'an is he who is deluded.	0.32
0.25-0.30	7	56:10	And the foremost, the foremost.	And the forerunners, the forerunners -	0.25
0.20-0.35	5	70:16	Extracting the contents of the marrow bones.	A remover of exteriors.	0.22
0.15-0.20	4	74:29	A tablet for mankind	Blackening the skins.	0,15
0.10-0.15	1	88:3	Amilatun Nasibatun	Working [hard] and exhausted	0.11
0.05-0.10	1	75:25	You think that he would do with it poverty	Expecting that there will be done to them [something] backbreaking.	0.08